

On Word Permutations

ALEXANDER L. FLIS

flisunit@gmail.com

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Abstract

To an astronomical probability, we demonstrate that the prime motive in history is the LORD, with profound modern geopolitical implications. Please note this paper consists of scholarly research written as entertainment, a la Dante's Divine Comedy.

1 Overview

The following lists of anagrams reflect the intersection of possibility and the author's judgement, constructing linguistic graph clusters of significance. Self-contained anagrams are tighter than multidimensional manifolds, meaning establishing limits on and approximating their associated probabilities is algebraic. Constructed manually, these lists are imperfect, approximation itself being optimal in this context. Yet we see truth through glass.

2 Biblical Events

Adam and Eve: damned

Apple of knowledge: Paleogene, downfall, flagpole, goalkeep

Cain and Abel: cannibal

Noah's Arc: anchors

Tower of Babel: Aeroflot, Waterloo

Gilgamesh and Ishtar: almightiness, highlanders, timesharing

Gilgamesh: Ishmael

Abram and Sarai: Arabians

Abraham and Sarah: Brahmans, Ramadans

Sodom and Gomorrah: Goddamm

Abraham Isaac sacrifice: miscarries

Abraham and Ishmael: admirable, mishandle

Ishmael: Islam

Isaac and Rebecca: Caesarian

Jacob and Esau: abscond

Jacob and Leah: cajoled

Jacob and Rachel: candelabra

Leah and Rachel: headache

Israel and Joseph: depression

Shechem and Dinah: maidenhead

LORD and Job: Jordan, Orlando

Jonah and whale: landown

LORD'S Passover: vasopressor, dorsales (... doorsill), droolers, lassoes, leopards
 Moses ten commandments: stonemasons, commonsense, condensates
 Joshua at Jericho: haustoria (penetrates cell wall) echo
 Samson's Jawbone: banjoes, bemoans, Jameson, ... James bon(d)
 Samson and Delilah: admonishes, hollandaise, medallions, dandelions
 Menelaus and Helen: manhandles
 Agamemnon and Helen: manhandles
 Paris and Helen: philanders, panhandlers, adrenaline, dealership, headliners
 Ahab and Jezebel: bendable, enabled
 Boaz and Ruth: autobahn, handout
 Samuel and Saul: landless, unamused, madness
 David and Goliath: validation, Thailand
 David and Bathsheba: abstained, deviants, shithead
 Solomon and Absalom: monsoonal
 David and Solomon: diamonds
 Solomon's wisdom: Simmons
 Solomon and Sheba: manhandles, abandons, abdomens, baldness, boldness, bondless, bondsman, damnable, hosannas, manholes, Absalom, asshole, Sheldon, hosanna, Lebanon, lambdas, Omahas, Samson
 Nebuchadnezzar and Jeremiah: dehumanized, harebrained, hemicerebra (epilepsy), remaindered, undermanned
 Nebuchadnezzar: Nazarene
 Daniel and lion: dandelion
 Esther and Haman: headmaster, anathemas, harshened, mandatees, meatheads
 Hanukkah candles: unshackled
 Caesar and Cleopatra: accelerators, consecrated, carpenters, copartners
 Judas and Jesus: sadness
 Pilate and Jesus: Japanese slut
 Arthur and Guinevere: heartrending, tragedienne
 Guinevere and Lancelot: overindulgence
 Arthur and Lancelot: adulterator
 Jesus's Resurrection: intercourse, sorceresses, countesses, crustiness, incestuous
 Old Covenant: colonnade
 New Covenant: nonevent
 Jesus Messiah: masseuse, missuses
 Jesus Christ: hussies
 Mary Magdalene: marmalade (citrus... clementine)
 Prophet Mohammed: hampered, tampered, homemade, mothered, Dorothea, moderate, hothead, DOORMAT
 Mary and Joseph: handsomer, pomander, jeopardy, syphoned, Adamson, Jameson, Jordan, Jonah
 Immaculate Conception: calumnation
 Jesus and Magi: gaudiness, misjudges, dinguses, Gaussian, Judaism
 John the Baptist: obstinate, obstipate (constipate severely), absinthe, phoniest, siphonet
 Jesus walking on water: rationaleness
 Jesus healing sick: gaucheness, hijackings
 Jesus multiplies bread: adulteresses, disreputable, dissimulates, absurdities, bestseller, implausible
 Jesus raising the dead: uresiesthesia (the desire to urinate)
 Iesus Nazarenus Rex Iudaeorum: murderousness

Jesus prophet: prophetess

Jesus ascending: secundines (afterbirth), gaudiness, jaundices, nuisances

Jesus and Satan: nauseant, unassent, Judas, Santa

Judas hanging on tree: neurasthenia, shotgunning, untarnished, antiheroes, authorised, dethroning

Jesus and Saul: usualness, dulness, Judases, sadness, saunaed, sunless, unseals, Juneau

Gospel of Judas: spadefuls (manure), apologue, fossulae (holes), DEGAUSS, DEPOSAL, flossed, GODLESS, JEALOUS, plagued, plussed, spoofed, ... Gauss fooled

3 Biblical Phrases

"King of Kings Lord of Lords": FOLKSINGING, dislodging, Klondiking, FIDDLINGS, gridirons, grillings, infolding, DINGDONG (ring a bell), dinornis (bird), doodling, drooling, FILLINGS, flooding, FLOSSING, forgings, fringing, frisking, gillions (billions), girdling (kill tree), glossing (polish), gridding (matrix), griffins, grokking (intuition), grossing, ignoring, killings, kindling, lordling, nigrosin (black), nonrigid, Ringling (circus), riddling, signings, skiffing (Thames), slinking, SLINGING

"The LORD and His Anointed": denationalised, internationals, nonresidential, nontraditional, disorientated, NETHERLANDISH, annihilators, aristotelian, orientalised

"Death Destroyer of Nations": faintheartedness (shy), defenestration (Thurn, anti-Catholic), forehandedness, adrenosterone, anaesthetised, fatheadedness, reforestation, transforation (pierce, ... Pierce Brosnan James Bond, bore, ... bore into Dark One's prison WOT), deteriorated, detestations, disheartened, Eratosthenes (polymath), entertainers, featheriness, foreordained, hydantoinate (treat Epilepsy), nonfederated, NORTHEASTERN, reorientates, restorations, synarthrodia (immovable), testosterone, tetrahedrons (pyramid), thereafter, trendsetters, ethisterone, radiosondes (weather balloons), reassertion, refashioned, resonations, restoration, retardation, retorsiones, shirtfronts, softhearted, storefronts, tearstained, tenderfoots, tenderheart, threadiness, threatener, tyranniser, adroitness, antiheroes, Stentorian

"Angel of Death": halogenated (acid), galeated (hooded), gatefold, goaltend, headgate (cattle), elegant, fagoted, gentled, loathed, negated, fanged, gaoled, golden, legend, agent, alone, atone, Godel, hedge, Helen, Hodge, Adel, Eden, Leah, Leda, Noah, ALF, eel, Tao, ... Eden gaol, Leah tangoed, Noah deflate/defeat/fated, Noah Adel ET, Helen daft/data/goad/goat/toad, hedge NATO, Godel Athena, Hodge fatale, legend AO, atone glade, Leda thong, felon Agathe (enchantress of Beauty and the Beast)

"King of Israel": folksinger, seignorial

finagler, forsaken, Friesian (Dutch horse), gasoline, ringlike, seraglio, slinkier, Kringle, Galois, goalie, reason, rifles, Saigon, Alfie, angel, Ariel, Erika, Koran, Rakel, siren, sling, Sloan, snail, snake, FLIS, Karl, lion, Loki, Rose.

... Flis oak reign, Earl King, sofa Klinger, Kaiser lion, Karl ignis/genii, Feliks ring AO, King Alf Rose, Alfie King, Kris goalie, Kris angel, Galois knifer, King AO rifles, Saigon rifle, Sloan grief, Ariel oinks, Erika flings/losing, Rakel finis, siren fail/flog/gaol/goal/Kali/loaf, Erik AO sling, snake flog/foil/frig/frog/girl, snail grief/Erik/frog, Loki farseing, finger Kali

"Queen of Israel": laniferous (wool bearing), equaliser, felonies, nefarious ... Que Alfie Rose

"Jesus of Nazareth": aeronauts, arsenates, authoress, NOSFERATU (vampire, BATTY), nauseates, otherness, resonates, Sauternes (wine), seafronts, serjeants, softeners, southerners, transfuse, unearthes, ... assentor, earnesters, enthuses, ersatzes, fateness, feasters, FEATHERS, foetuses, fortunes, fourteen, freshest, furanose, Hortense (Tennessee), HARENESS, hastener, haunTERS, heartens, hoarsens, honester, housesat, huntress, jousters, neofetus, neuroses, onrushes, RATENESS (excellence), rehouses, SHERATAN (second brightest star in Aries: Hamal, Sheratan, Mesarthim, 41 Arietis), SHERATON, saunters, seafront, seahorse, seashore, seasoner, senators, serenata, serjeant, shareout, shortens, shouters, southern, southers (golf), Theresa, tonsures (scalp), treasons, true-ness, urethane (plastic), ... aureate, austere, authors, Easters, fathers, neuters, tensors, thrones, trashes, unseats, Arjuna, Athena, Athens, Atreus, harass, Saturn, Tehran, throne, haute, Santa, Satan, Torah, torus, Hera, Rose, Ruth, Shae, shot, surf, Thor, taro, tsar, UFOS, USAF, USSR, Tao, USA

"Judas Iscariot": adjustors, auditoria, diastasic (abdominal separation in women over 35), JUSTICIAR, sudatoria (Roman steambath)

Asiatics, Asturias (Spain), acidosis, Adriatic (sea, East of Italy), custodia, diarists, Judaists, JURASSIC, judicata (no appeal), judoists, juristic, sadistic, surcoats, TRIASSIC

4 US Presidents

George Washington: segregation

Thomas Jefferson: freemasons, menoraheS

Benjamin Franklin: Menkalinan (star)

Alexander Hamilton: Athenian dollar

Benedict Arnold: dandelion

Andrew Jackson: Korean cans

Abraham Lincoln: MONARCHIAL, nonracial, ALHAMBRA, HAIRBALL, Hamilcar, HANNIBAL, Marianna

Ulysses S Grant: sugarless, sultaness, greyness, rustless, saltiness, slyness, Saturn, lunar, regal, guns, guts, tyre

Hiram Ulysses Grant: synergist marshal, Lutheranisms, manslaughter, salutariness, harassments, languishers, naturalises, ringmasters, ultramarine, gunsmithes

Theodore Roosevelt Jr: retroverted, overlord

Thomas Woodrow Wilson: dominator, harmonist, moralist, Romanist, DOORMAT

Franklin Delano Roosevelt: Frankenstein, federational, overinflated, revelational

John Fitzgerald Kennedy: kindheartedly, freehandedly, endearingly, enlightened, lionhearted, NONFEDERATE

***Lyndon Baines Johnson: BLOODINESS JOHNNY ANN

Richard Milhous Nixon: honour criminal, Hiroshima cloud, criminaloid, dishonour, Indochina, Hiroshima, moronical, nonsocial, rancorous, unscholar

Ronald Wilson Reagan: Wagnerian (voice), annealing, erosional, graniose, loosening, nondollar, worsening, wrongdoer

George Herbert Washington Bush: northeastern, noteworthiness, southeasterner, southwesterner, interrogators, nongregarious, regenerations, retrogression, straighteners, strengtheners

George Washington Bush: unworthiness, haughtiness, naughtiness, segregation, whorehouses
Donald John Trump: photomural, haplodont (MOLAR tooth), hormonal, nonadult, nonmoral, odourant, thraldom, unpardon, DOORMAT, dropout, Hampton, harpoon, hoodlum, humoral, lampoon, manhunt, tornado, adolph, author, dotard, harlot, Jordan

5 World Figures

Princess Diana: narcissine, radiancies, rancidness, acridness, ascarides (parasitic worm), Cassandre, dispraise, epicardia, epicrania, Parisians, paradises, piscaries (fishing), praesidia, precisian, raininess, randiness, rapidness, Sardinian, Spaniards, sarcinaes (cocci bacteria)

Queen Elizabeth: equitable, bequeath, equalize, hazelnut, quantize, thebaine (opiate), tuneable, zenithal

Margaret Thatcher: greatheart

Osama bin Laden: Islamabad

Mifepristone (abortion): profeminist, mortifies, petrifies

OJ Simpson: poisons

Orenthal James Simpson: loathsomeness, metamorphosis, momentariness, phenomenalism, rationaleness

William Shakespeare: Herakles Impales, Messiah Aerial, ellipse kaiser wham/ham/haw/maw

Darwin's evolution: idolatrous

"Money is the root of all evil": overestimation, televisionally, revelationist

(Ch)ervona ryta: (Ch)ort Eva YNA (r)

Holocaust: cahoots, locust, Claus, lotus, oaths

Holodomyr: drool (tEp MIT), horol (time), moldy (plague), moody (Hank), holy doom

ChatGPT: Ptah

6 Locations

El Paso Texas: aesop exalts, atlas expose, apostles axe, apostaxes

Pasadena California: paradisical, craniospinal

Cambridge Massachusetts: Messerschmidt (Middle High German words mezzar "knife" + smit "smith"), acmaesthesia (anesthesia), metastasises (cancer). [MIT logo Smith, McCormick (reaper) all girls dorm]

Detroit Michigan: admitting coheir, admitting heroic, airtight demonic, chimera dittoing, decimation right, diatomite Grinch, digametic Thorin, dogmatic inherit, Grinch meditatio, hinged triatomic, hidrotic tegmina, homicide rattling, idiot rematching, ignited trichoma, mariticide thong, mintage trichoid, miotic threading, teaming trichoid, tegmina trichoid, ... antiheroic, crimated, chondrite (meteor), mithridate (poison antidote), dictation, nightmare

Grosse Pointe Park, (Michigan): progenitress, perestroika, artinesser, OPPRESSION, patronises, pranksters, properness, prospering, REPRESSION, ... antipornographies, cinematographies, roentgenographic, promonarchists

Washington District of Columbia: antifuoridationists, constitutionalism, industrialisation, antiabortionists, CHRISTIANISATION, discriminational, institutionalism, traditionalistic, antimilitarists, ANTIMONARCHISTS, bioastronautics, CATHOLICISATION, colonisationist, disorganisation, fractionisation, malconstruction, rancidification, romanticisation, stratifications

Jerusalem Israel: Ijsselmeer (lake off Amsterdam), lamaseries, surrealism, ruleless, samurais, aerals

7 Schools

Caltech: Catch El, cachet (respected, admired), chalet (wooden house in Swiss Alps), thecal (spinal sheath), catch, cheat, leach, latch, teach, Alec, Cale, Leah (J), Che

California Institute of Technology: CENTRIFUGALISATION (separate wheat from chaff), electro-coagulation (destroy tumors), configurationally, constitutionality, INTERNATIONALIST, NEURASTHENICALLY (physical and mental exhaustion), catholicisation, congratulations, contortionistic, hallucinogenics, HELIOCENTRICITY, nonconciliatory, orientaliation

Harvard College: OVERCHARGED, cellarage, clearhead, corralled (confine), gravelled, grovelled, lalorrhea (babble), overlarge, overreach, hardcore, Lovelace, Rachele (G)

Harvard Extension School: conservatoire, Netherlandish, rationaleness

Harvard Medical School: haemorrhoids, hemorrhoidal

Harvard Law School: ?

Harvard University: distrainer (seize property), Dysarthria (slurred speech), hairdryers, hydrastine, indurative (sclerotic) irradiates, Stradivari, ARTHURIAN, tarnished

Massachusetts Institute of Technology: anesthesiologists, semiconsciousness, unenthusiastical, unostentatiously, emotionlessness, thoughtlessness

The Great Dome: trematode (flatworm parasite, fluke), garotted, geometer, Dorthea, theorem

Sloan School of Management: melanomatoses (aggressive cancer), collagenosis (connective tissue disease), thalamocoele (third ventricle [hole] of brain), commonsense, malfeasance, somnolences, Tallahassee (Florida)

University of Michigan (M): reunifications, fractionising

Oxford University: ironfisted, routinised, TOXIFEROUS, understory, frontiers

Cambridge University: recriminative, abridgements, discriminate, eviscerating, intermediacy, misadventure, misdirecting, miseducating

Trinity College: erectility, gentility, glycerine, integrity, intellect, intercity, lettering

Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich: reticuloendothelioses (avian virus), counterinsurgencies, counterintelligence, cytodifferentiation, tetrachloroethylene (dry cleaning), unconstitutionality, contradistinctions, deconstructionists, institutionalising, reconstructionists, reticuloendothelia (immune response), trichostrongylosis (parasite)

Ecole Polytechnique (Paris): equipollency (equal in power), chylopoetic (churn into juice), phlyctenule (eye irritation), collection, eloquently, telephonic

Moscow State University: overestimation, oversystematic, VICTORIOUSNESS, atrociousness, autoeroticism, eviscerations, insectivorous, monstrosities, ovariectomise, reconstitutes, resuscitative, sociometrists, transvestites, VERACIOUSNESS, vicariousness, voraciousness

Todai: toad, Ito, Tao

Tokyo University: virtuosity, introitus (opening), intrusive, nervousity, notoriety, nutritive, onerosity, orientist, routinise, seniority, strikeout, Tinkertoy (good for children)

Hong Kong University: inventorying (take stock), nonstriking, shotgunning, unshrinking, vertiginous, enshrining, enthroning, inventions, nourishing, outshining, overnights, reinvoking, rethinking, roughening, shortening, snookering, theorising, toughening

Tel Aviv University: neutralities, universality, eventuality, intrusively, intuitively, investitive, iteratively, nutritively, ventilative, versatility, INSULARITY, invasively, nativities, RELATIVITY,

revitalise, revivalist, vitalities

Institute for Advanced Studies: adventitiousness, unattractiveness, adventurousness, anfractuosit-
ies (winding), considerateness, counterfeitness, defenestrations, destructiveness, dissatisfaction,
distinctiveness, instructiveness, interactiveness, neuroscientists, stratifications, Russianisation

Institut des Hautes Etudes Scientifiques: authenticities, unenthusiastic, attitudinised, destitute-
ness, disinfectants, dissentientes, infecundities (barren), quintessences

Cranbrook Kingswood (High School): snowboarding (starts AVALANCHE), absconding, bor-
rowings, cornrowing, knockdowns, backwoods, boardings, boondocks, brainwork, brickwork,
ironwoods, ironworks, sorrowing, woodgrain (poly)

Cass Technical High School: cholangiectasis (releasing bile), ESCHATOLOGICAL (Holy Judge-
ment), schoolteaching, callisthenics (gym), legalisations (marijuana), localisations, lochioschesis
(afterbirth vaginal discharge), neoclassicist

8 Countries

North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (UK spelling): laryngotracheitis (avian herpes), olecranarthri-
tis (ELbow arthritis), REINCARNATIONIST, transcontinental, TRINITROGLYCERIN, ANTAGO-
NISTICAL, CHATTELISATION (RACIAL SLAVERY), gelatinisation, integrationist, INTRANSI-
GENTLY (UNCOMPROMISING), osteoarthritic, REGISTRATIONAL, reorganisation, cartelisation,
charlatanries, totalitarians

North Atlantic Treaty Organization (US spelling): CONTAINERIZATION, internationality, TRINI-
TROGLYCERIN, INTERROGATIONAL, nationalization, rationalization, categorization, centraliza-
tion, CHANNELIZATION, INTENTIONALITY, nanotechnology, nonrecognition, RECOLONIZA-
TION, TERRITORIALITY, ANGLICIZATION, intraarterial, intratracheal, irrationality, LATROCI-
NATION (ROBBERY), NARCOTIZATION, nonirritating, nontheatrical, orthogonality, ratiocination
(logic), REINCARNATION, TANTALIZATION, ANNIHILATION, antiheroical, antirational, anti-
thetical, CARTHAGINIAN, canonization

United States of America: anfractuositities (winding), mucoenteritides, densitometries, DRAMATI-
SATIONS, satisfaciendum (legal arrest), traumatisations, underestimates, administrates, counter-
feited, disorientates, documentaries, educationists, intermediates, manufactories, misinstructed,
reconstituted, testificandum (appear in court), testudinate (tortoise), destitute

The Pentagon: pantheon, PATHOGEN, neonate

Central Intelligence Agency: antiallergenic, entertainingly, CANCERIGENIC, crenellating (battle-
ments of castle), gigantically, ... CANCELLING TITAN EEL REGENCY

The White House (Oval Office - Elliptic): whiteouts, outhits, outwits, ethos

Senate and House of Representatives: unrepresentative, unresponsiveness, antidepressants,
defenestrations, openheartedness, pretentiousness, restorativeness, SENTENTIOUSNESS, soft-
heartedness, unanaesthetised, urethrostenoses

The Supreme Court: spectrometer, CORRUPTTEST, persecutor, prometheus, retrospect, stepmother,
threescore, trumpeters, humourers, mercurous, potterers, putterers, superhero

United States Treasury: ?

Israel: sailer, Ariel, Aries, earl, Sire, seal, aisle, liers, slier, Leia, Risa

Mossad: Samos, Dams, Sam, Mao

Palestine: penalties, tapelines, Pilates, penal

Palestine vs Israel: separateness, priestliness

Saudi Arabia: absurd, braids, disbar, rabid, radius, auras, Arius, sura, bud

UKRAINE: URINE, aurin (Neverending Story), kauri (tree), nikau (tree), KAIN (kills brother), KANE, rank

Russia: Arius (God the Father), auris (listen), risus (no rules), sura, Sir, USA, USS

Committee for State Security: cystoureteritis, micrometeorites, certificatory, crematoriums, meritocratic, ossificatory, sociometrist

Komitet Gosudarstvennoy Bezopasnosti: undemonstrativeness, venoperitoneostomy, parsimoniousness, underestimations, unresponsiveness

The Kremlin: netlike, thinker, tinker, ermine (judge), hermit, kernel (Putin), Merkel, Merlin, Helen

The Federal Assembly: BREATHALYSED, breastfeeds, deathlessly, featherless, headmasters, heartlessly, fatherless, fearlessly, featherbed, leaderless, marshalled

Wagner Private Military Company: anticomplementary, inappreciatively, TRINITROGLYCERIN, interrogatively, malpractitioner, plenipotentiary

"Crimea Russian": cinerarium, miscarries, sinecurism, massacrer, MESSIANIC, Caesarism, America

Messia uranic/auric/aurin/Carin/cairn/curia/runic/uncia

America ruins/sins

"Crimea Ukrainian": cinerarium, uncinaria (parasite), Marianna, America

Marianna ickier/icier

America unair

People's Republic of China: councillorship, prosencephalic (forebrain), albocinereous (grey and white brain matter), chancellories, porcellaneous, calliphorine (flies), necrophilous, honourifical, polariscopic, porocephalus (parasitic worm)

Republic of China Taiwan: reunification, unpracticable

Republic of India: unclarified, filaricide (anti-parasite), unfordable, unpacified

Brazil: libra (scales), Rabi, rial, Rab

South Africa: fractious, haustoria, archaist

South America: Oireachtas (freemen assembly), amateurish, eucharist, moustache

African Union: unicorn

BRICS (gold): cribs, Cris, bris (circumcision), ribs, Bic (pen), CBS, Sir, Sri

European Union: Neronian (pope), neuron, pioneer, unprune, unripe, preunion, prounion

Australia: Alastair, lariats, rituals, astral

Japan Nihon: aphonia (inability to speak Ariel), anopia (no eyes), johnin (treat leprosy), Hanna (NATHAN), Hanoi (NATHAN), JONAH, piano, jinn, NOAH, pain

Roman Catholic Church: acronarcotic (opiate of the masses), calumniator, chlorinator, chromatical, intraocular, micrococcal (bubbly), monarchical, ochlocratic (government by mob), trichomonal (parasitic STI)

Stato della Citta del Vaticano: occidentalised, vasodilatation (old), collectivised, devotionalist, violoncellist

Commonwealth of Australia, Russian Federation, North Korea, Iran ???

9 Modern People

Alexander Luka Flis (2502 words): FLEURDELIS, unrealised, unsalaried, Afrikaans (Dutch), Airedales (King of Terriers), Andalusia (Seville, Spain), ALKALISED (HERO), ALLELUIAS, enfilades (column of gunfire), Falklands (UK), feudalise, fusillade (concentrated gunfire), killdeer (bird), landfall, LAURELLED, RAFAEL, rainfalls, reinfused, rekindles, unrelaxed arsenide, dallier, Eurasian, Federals, Flanders (Ned), failures, funeral, funereal, INDEXER, lakeside, SEINFELD, skillful, sneakier, sneerful, sullener, unafraid, unallied, undefile, UNSEALED, unslaked Aurelia, aerials, alien, asexual, asunder, darken, eureka, feller, ferule, fideles, FIELDS, KERNEL, killer, Lauren, Linux, leaker, redskin, refined, residue, Saladin (?... Aladdin?), saurian, skeined (knotted), skulled, Ukraine

Ariel, Delila, Frank, Enkidu, Erika, Faisal, Israel, Kali, Keller, kaiser, linear, Neruda, nailer, neural, Selena, Sindel, Aldin, Diana, drake, Euler, Felix, fells, Isaak, Karl, KEANU, KLAUS, Klein, Lexus, lunar, nexus, naked, nukes, Raina, Rakel, RADIX, reeks, Saudi, Snell, Sulla, sarin, sauna, siren, Uriel, earl, Ides, kids, lief, seer, sid, NASA, USAF, DNA, FDA, NRA, NSA, NSF, USA, UK

Alexander Luka Neva (Nevsky):

Georgia Neva Flis (2506 words):

Marianna Flis: Arianism, mainsail, MALARIAN, FILARIA (elephantiasis, tropical disease via mosquitoes), FRISIAN (Netherlands, ... Thurn and Taxis), Iranian, infamia, marinas (DYC), marlins (Florida), Samaria (Israel), Armani, Faisal, Ismail, mafias, NARNIA (Prince Rillian ... brilliant in the Silver Chair), Samara (Russia), Samian (Samos Phoenecian "high"), salaam, simian (monkey, zodiac), Asian, Farsi, Finns, Islam, Siam (J)

Marianna Lukovna Flis: Ukrainians, VILLAINOUS, Afrikaans (Dutch), Allianora (Espionage Agent of Chrysalis Organization), Louisiana (J), molluskan, Slavonian, Arkansan (J), illusion, infamous, klansman, MANORIAL, MILLIONS, Murasaki (purple), Nikolai (Romanov), nirvana, unfilial, visional, Alaskan, alkalis, annular, luminal, lunaria, MANSION, MINIONS, ovarial, silvian, samovar, samurai, saurian, savior, skilful, solaria, Uranian, unmoral, unrival, Asimov, Avalon, fusion, Kalila, Korans, llamas, Lilian, Markus, salmon, slolem

Marianna Juska (1st husband): Ramanujan

Anna Blisch (nee): HANNIBAL, clannish, Caliban (and Ariel), chablis (steely wine), ASLAN (Narnia), Chiba, China, Isaac, Lhasa, Nisan, snail

Anna Ivanova Blisch: cannabinoil, anabolic, basilica, CASANOVA

Anna Flys: annals, ALFY, nasa, nsa nsf, sly, SLAY ANN F

Vladimir Vladimirovich Putin: undiplomatic, palindromical, radioactinium, unidiomatic (spy), archipallium (deep mind), dilapidation, acidulation, calliphorid (fly), caluminator, criminaloid, humiliation, ILLUMINATOR, invalidator, lacrimation (tears), manipulator, multiracial, PATRI-MONIAL, PIARACHNOID (SPY), PURITANICAL, machinator, MONARCHIAL, MULTIPOLAR, PLUTOMANIA, provincial, TRIUMVIRAL (Marcus Licinius Crassus ... criminals, assassins, Russians, samurais), undramatic, validation, vindicator, ARTHURIAN, MacArthur, LUNATICAL,

paramount, Victorian, PLATINUM

10 Mathematicians

Georg Cantor: coronate, coronae, coroner, creator, grantor, octagon, Cretan, carrot, cornea, gorgon, rector

Kurt Godel: grouted (tiles), ergot, lord, rod kludge

Emmy Noether: theorem

Carl Friedrich Gauss (Q): circularisers

Srinivasa Ramanujan (M): marijuana, Arianism, Iranians, MARIANNA, nirvana, samurai, Varanasi, Jainism, marinas, Russian, Uranian, Arjuna [liked fractions]

Alexander Grothendieck (6665 words)

Alexander Grothendieck aka (N)athaniel: [ANTICHRIST] [Utah...haut "high", IHES] grandchildren, redeclaration, reenlightened, heartrending, largehearted, Netherlander, reincarnated, cheerleader, clearheaded, kindhearted, leatherneck, lionhearted, darkhaired, dragonhead, eradicator, arachnoid, archangel, Dexedrine, dandelion, dandering, datelined, deathlike, dethroned, diarrheal, diarrhoea, enchanted, enthroned, gladiator, kindheart, lionheart, ordinance, Rhineland, tangerine, Athenian, anointer, anorexic, calendar, Creator, darkhair, Ragnarok

dethroned King Carl/Alex
dethroned Kringle/Klinger/Earl King
dethroned kernel/general

ARCHANGEL DEXEDRINE
X-archangel Odin reeked
Archangel dented Erik
Archangel Eden editor/rioted/TRIKED
Deathlike Dragon
DANDELION GATHERER
gladiator reeked
lionheart renegade
Creator Kleenex Gandhi
Ragnarok declined
enchanted Godlike rare
enthroned garlicked
enlightened record
exonerating Rachel
decode rex (N)ATHANIEL

Netherlander dockage

cheerleader dating
leatherneck dreading/ordained GX
leatherneck dander
lionheart redneck
Erika goaltender

FINAL FANTASY (N): ANNALIST (N), fantails (birds), fantasia, lantanas (weeds), NATAN (Nathan), NASALITY (J) ... ANALYST, falsify, falsity, infants, nastily, saintly, stiffly, TIFFANY (Matrix 4), FAISAL, Stalin, Tainan (Taiwan), Aslan, Atlas, Finns, fatal, Nisan, Santa, Satan, salty, Talia, Yalta, Alan, Alf, Anna, anal, FIAT, slay, Stan, ALF, SAA, Yin ...NATAN falsify/fails/flay/ALF NASAL Tiffany/Fiat/Fain/Tiff Faisal fanny Santa Alf Fiat Alf Ann Aslan Tiffany Atlas Finn Saint Alf fan Nisan fatal FIAT SLAY ANN F (Baba: Slay Ann F)

11 Quotations

"I am the LORD, and there is no other, The One forming light and creating darkness, Causing well-being and creating calamity; I am the LORD who does all these." (Isaiah 45:6-7)

"So many peoples and mighty nations will come to seek the LORD of hosts in Jerusalem and to entreat the favor of the LORD."

"Thus says the LORD of hosts, 'In those days ten men from all the nations will grasp the garment of a Jew saying, "Let us go with you, for we have heard that God is with you.'"" (Zechariah 8:22-23)

[LOGICIAN] The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars; Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces the cedars of Lebanon. (Psalm 29:5)

The LORD possessed me at the beginning of His way, Before His works of old. From everlasting I was established (Proverbs 8:22-23)

For He is coming to judge the earth. (1 Chronicles 16:33)

12 Conclusions

We have demonstrated the LORD'S omnipresence. This verifies the Taoist parable that not knowing is true knowledge, and the First Commandment that idolatry falls far short of divinity. We anticipate these patterns to be maintained across languages around the world, a fertile area of further inquiry.

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